

ANALYSIS OF ORGANOLEPTIC CHARACTERISTICS AND RECOVERY PROPERTIES (REHYDRATION PROCESS) OF PUMPKIN CONCENTRATE

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Abstract. *Melon products, in particular, are obtained by separating the primary and secondary pulp of pumpkin fruits, cleaning them, treating them with ascorbic acid (freezing), drying them using sublimation and convective methods, and grinding them into powder using a grinding machine. The secondary pulp of the product, which has a color property, is used in the garment and textile industry to dye various clothes, fabrics, and yarn products, reducing the cost of finished products by about 1-1.5 times.*

Keywords: *primary and secondary mass, peel, freezing, powder, organoleptic.*

The gourd family includes 800 species distributed in almost all regions of the world. There are 18 naturally occurring species of this family in the flora of Uzbekistan. They are pollinated by ants, thrips, bees and other insects. Most of the female flowers are shed and form 2-5 fruits that ripen on a stalk. Inside the fruit of the plant there is a cavity (nest), where the seeds are attached to the ovary with the help of threads (placenta). The fruit is a drupe of various shapes, colors and sizes (usually large), many-seeded, smooth and juicy. It blooms in June-September, and the fruit ripens in August-October. The pectin substances contained in pumpkin have a good effect on intestinal inflammatory diseases, helping to remove bacteria and toxic substances from the intestines, and preventing dehydration in diseases accompanied by diarrhea. At the same time, pumpkin also accelerates the excretion of cholesterol from the body. Therefore, it is recommended to include pumpkin in the daily diet of patients with cardiovascular diseases (atherosclerosis, hypertension), chronic colitis and enterocolitis, severe (rapid) and chronic nephritis, pyelonephritis, cholecystitis, gallstones and jaundice (hepatitis). Pumpkin is also useful as a dietary food, especially for the elderly and young children. Pumpkin juice has a calming effect and improves sleep, and is a good remedy against vomiting (including raw pumpkin), especially against vomiting in pregnant women.

The process of obtaining pumpkin juice consists of several main stages: preparation, crushing, squeezing and filtration. During the preparation stage, the pumpkin is cleaned and brought to the required condition. Then, after the pumpkin is crushed, the squeezing process begins, in which mechanical or hydraulic squeezing methods are used to extract the pumpkin liquid. After squeezing, the resulting juice is filtered, which serves to increase its purity and quality. There are many scientific studies on the richness of pumpkin juice with biologically active substances, vitamins and minerals, and its beneficial effects on health. This juice is important for

its antioxidant, anti-inflammatory and immune-boosting properties. When assessing the quality of pumpkin juice, a number of indicators are important, including:

Chemical composition: Vitamins (e.g., vitamins A and C), minerals and organic acids.

Organoleptic properties: Taste, smell and color.

Microbiological safety: The juice is tested for the presence of bacteria, fungal spores and other microorganisms.

Also, the consumption of pumpkin juice helps to improve metabolic processes in the body and regulate gastrointestinal function. When assessing the quality of pumpkin juice, indicators such as its chemical composition, organoleptic properties and microbiological safety are important. The use of pumpkin juice in the food industry creates opportunities for expansion, especially in beverages and food products, through innovative approaches. At the same time, the development of technology for extracting juice from pumpkin melon products is necessary for the efficient use of agricultural resources and ensuring sustainable development. This process plays an important role in increasing the many benefits and economic value of pumpkin. This technology ensures the proper utilization of pumpkin melon products and improves product quality. The use of pumpkin juice in the food industry plays an important role in increasing its versatile benefits and economic value. The rehydration levels of primary and secondary product samples of pumpkin are shown in Figure 1 below.

Figure-1. Graph of rehydration of primary and secondary dried pumpkin product samples

Practical experiments.

Selection of raw materials: To obtain pumpkin juice, it is first necessary to select high-quality and ripe pumpkin fruits. Usually, sweet and high-liquid varieties are preferred.

Inspection. The selected raw materials are subjected to organoleptic and physicochemical analysis. Products contaminated with various pests and rotten as a result of biological reactions are separated.

Cleaning: Before extracting the juice from the pumpkin, its outer covering (stem and skin) is cleaned. This process is important for cleaning it from microorganisms and chemicals.

Mechanical preparation:

Grinding: The obtained pumpkin fruits undergo a crushing process. This process is important for the efficiency of the press, increasing the efficiency of juice extraction. The pumpkin structure is broken down into smaller particles by means of crushing devices (e.g., crushers).

Pressing process: The crushed pumpkin is pressed. This process uses mechanical or hydraulic pressing methods. As a result of the pressing process, the pumpkin liquid is separated from the solid residue (pulp).

Filtration: After the pressing process, the juice obtained is filtered. This process helps in removing solid residues and microorganisms from the juice, resulting in a clean and quality juice.

Processing: If necessary, long-term storage options are considered by low-temperature sterilization or low-pressure processing of the juice. This process ensures that the juice is free from toxic substances and extends its shelf life.

Storage: The juice obtained is stored in well-sealed containers. Storage conditions (temperature, light) have a significant impact on the quality of the juice.

Figure 2. Analysis of organoleptic characteristics and recovery properties (rehydration process) of pumpkin concentrate.

The technology of extracting juice from pumpkin is not only an effective way to diversify agricultural products, but also to prepare healthy drinks. The pumpkin juices obtained through this process are rich in vitamins, minerals and antioxidants, which help improve the overall health of the body. The nutritional value of pumpkin, its use as a hot and cold drink, as well as its role in the development of local production, play an even more important role. At the same time, the process of extracting juice from pumpkin can cause less harm to the environment, use agricultural resources more efficiently, and economically develop agricultural activities. Nowadays, the increasing demand for healthy nutrition and food quality is gaining importance, which indicates

that the future of pumpkin drinks is bright. Therefore, it is necessary to develop scientific research and innovation to make the technology of extracting juice from pumpkin more attractive and expand it.

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